

Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka

wydanie specjalne

Warszawa

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(wydanie specjalne) Volume-2, № 5 October 2022

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NEW METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN TO STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Berdieva Mukarrama Anvarovna

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences,
Associate Professor, Head of the Russian Language Department of the
Kimyo International University in Tashkent,
m.berdiyeva@ytit.uz

Abstract. The idea of humanization and humanitarization of education is becoming a priority in our society. The need to integrate technical and humanitarian knowledge, the ways of such a synthesis is actively discussed by teachers of higher education. The university should produce a specialist with a high cultural level, which was often emphasized by well-known methodologists. The following article is devoted to the innovative methods of teaching Russian in higher education institutions.

Keywords: method, methodology, digital technology, perception, speech, rhythm, speed, melody.

INTRODUCTION

Our century is the "information age", "the age of new technologies", "the age of education". The development of education remains one of the priority state directions, since it is high-quality education that is the basis of the innovative development of any country. The modernization of the education system, the ongoing changes in the system of higher education are due to the movement towards an innovative personality-developing paradigm of education, the need to use the intellectual and creative potential of a person for creative activity in all spheres of life. The change in the content of education consists in a gradual transition from educational and subject-based activities based on the assimilation of the fundamentals of sciences, knowledge, skills and habits, to a focus on the mastery of each student (taking into account the characteristics of his development) in aggregate universal skills.

The construction of the content of education, taking into account modern trends in the development of scientific knowledge, leads to the need, as the main units of assimilation, to single out not only concepts, but also those cognitive means that help the student independently acquire knowledge through mastery of intellectual actions that develop thought processes.

The general didactic principles of teaching are: the principle of scientific character, structure and consistency in teaching; the principle of connection between theory and practice; the principle of interdependence of different sections that make up the school course of the Russian language (spelling, punctuation, grammar with a dictionary, etc.); consciousness, the principle of action; the principle of appearance, durability and

convenience; the principle of individual approach to students.

- A) the relationship between language learning and thinking development;
- (b) the relationship between the study of the grammatical structure of a language and the acquisition of literary reading skills;
- c) the interrelationship between the study of grammar and the acquisition of speaking skills, and so on.

1. The application of the scientific principle of language teaching implies the provision of students only such knowledge - information about the language, which is firmly established in modern linguistics, the coverage of these phenomena in their interdependence and development.

For example, once in Russian textbooks I, o, e were called soft vowels, which are incorrect from the point of view of modern science, and therefore they are now letters denoting sounds, a, y, e or previous softness (ja, jy, je).

2. In a broad sense, the connection between theory and practice is the relevance of teaching to life, the ability to apply the knowledge acquired in school in practical production and social activities.

3. One of the major shortcomings of the organization of Russian language classes at school is that grammar, spelling, punctuation, and sometimes stylistics are studied as completely independent sections, separated from each other.

4. From the syntax of learning morphology Students may not be able to list the conditions for separating the secondary members of a sentence, the knowledge is insufficient. At the same time, they are unable to distinguish written parts of speech with intonation, pauses, and punctuation in oral speech, and are unable to independently determine what new shade of meaning has been introduced. spoken by a given separated member of a sentence. Understood rule or definition is also not real knowledge. It is common for students to speak confidently about how passive and intransitive verbs or verbs of perfect and imperfect form differ, but without understanding the essence of these grammatical categories, they confuse them in practice. Therefore, when explaining a novelty, students should try to make sure that they really understand what is being explained to them and then they can consciously remember the material they need. It happens that memorizing something happens until you have real knowledge about this event. When the opportunity arises, it is possible to speed up the process of understanding what students have learned before by constantly returning to the same question in later lessons.

The level of mastery consciousness is determined by the level of activity of students and their interest in the work they do. The teacher's creative, unconventional use of different techniques and methods, the use of entertaining tasks on different tasks and exercises, pictures, tables, grammar material of different difficulty, helps to increase the activity of students in the Russian language classroom. stylistics and others.

5. Concretization of the abstract and generalization of significance in volume is an important condition for the successful acquisition of knowledge and skills in Russian by students. Concretization and generalization are achieved through the use of various

methods of visual representation of the studied material - tables, diagrams, graphs, etc. Applying the principle of precision is one of the most important conditions for consciously mastering the program material. students in Russian. The main content of this subject program is grammar in its theoretical part. Grammar, on the other hand, takes place in generalizing events, abstracting them from specific concrete events and facts. It is one of the abstract sciences that is very close to mathematics and logic by the specified criteria.

Strong knowledge of the Russian language can be given to students only if they are independent and, if possible, regularly incorporated creative work skills. winter teaches independent knowledge through observation of the surrounding reality. Independent work can only be seen as a task that requires students to think, act creatively, and overcome difficulties.

6.The degree of more or less use of the material is determined by the age of the students, their level of development, the nature of the material, as well as the method of its presentation. So, for example, the understanding of the following sentence, compound predicate, impersonal sentence is not clear for primary school students, there are no manuals and special definitions for 5th grade students.

However, all of these "difficult" knowledge and skills are not only available, but are well mastered by students with general development sufficient for a particular school age. And the concept of "difficulty" itself is very relative: what is difficult for some students turns out to be relatively easy for others, or is mastered without difficulty at all.

7.Taking into account the individual characteristics of students (abilities, inclinations, level of readiness, etc.) at the same time when applying the same methods, techniques and types of exercises to all students in the process of language teaching using the same requirements need

8.Continuity between different parts of education, its separate classes is one of the necessary conditions for successful teaching of the Russian language. The general didactic requirement is to ensure a normal transition from simple to complex, from easy to difficult in the learning process, to support the transition to the next, to take into account the logic of the topic. .

In addition to the above general didactic principles of teaching, there are a number of principles that are unique to the methodology of the Russian language.

- 1.Relying on the "sense of language";
- 2.Pay attention to the expressiveness of speech;
- 3.Compare written language with spoken language;
- 4.Focus on the linguistic issue;
- 5.Exercise of speech and writing organs;
- 6.Gradually increase the speed of language learning

The level of independence of students in the class is different. Depending on this, seminar elements, organized discussions, as well as help from older students to younger ones can be provided. Other forms can also be used, such as lectures, but it is very

problematic to use them in Russian lessons. In all of this, the type of course does not change - varieties emerge.

Lesson - seminar lesson. The specificity of the seminar is, firstly, in the self-preparation of students on a particular topic, secondly, in the reports of schoolchildren on these topics, and thirdly, in the discussion of all present for the audience and fourth, in drawing conclusions. discussion of the topic by the teacher. This form of teaching is most prudent in testing knowledge on a number of similar topics and in learning topics that students already know. After selecting a topic for such lessons, mark specific questions that students (3-4) will prepare five- to seven-minute reports using additional literature. The rest should repeat what they have learned on the topics covered in order to participate in the discussion of the friend's messages in class.

The methodology of teaching the Russian language (native) language at the university is an independent pedagogical science. Deep knowledge of methodology is a necessary condition for teacher training. A modern teacher should be well educated: be proficient in the norms of the literary language, have a good knowledge of the content and system of work on the Russian language at the university, the educational possibilities of the subject "Russian language", assimilate the theoretical foundations and principles of teaching the Russian language at the university, know the basic methodological methods of educational work and be able to apply them, know the leading directions in the development of methodology as a science, research of recent decades and problems awaiting their solution.

The modern stage of the development of civilization requires specialists with broad humanitarian thinking, able to build competently professional activities according to the laws of harmonious development. But we are talking not only about the fact that an engineering and technical worker must have a sufficient level of intellectual training in order to be able to ensure the effectiveness of his work. No less important is the fact that it is humanitarian knowledge that gives such priorities as responsibility for universally significant values, worldview self-determination, general cultural competence, personal self-actualization.

Teaching the Russian language should involve all aspects of students' speech activity. Speech activity is an active, purposeful process of transmitting or receiving a message mediated by the language system and determined by the situation of communication. This is a system of skills aimed at solving various communication problems. We are talking about communicative tasks, combined on the basis of the following features: a) the form of speech - oral or written; b) perception or generation of speech. Traditionally, speech activity is divided into 4 types: listening (oral, perception), speaking (oral, production), reading (writing, perception), writing (writing, production).

In modern methodology, there is a desire to bring the conditions of the educational process closer to the conditions of free communication. In this regard, much attention is paid to the development of skills in all four types of speech activity. There is such a term as interconnected learning, which involves the parallel and balanced formation of

four types of speech activity based on common language material within their sequential-temporal relationship. Listening, speaking, reading and writing is both a goal and a means of learning. Work on these types of speech activity is carried out in a certain sequence within the framework of a practical lesson or a cycle of classes, in which general language material is mandatory. In the communicative-activity approach, the most common methodological unit of the organization of language material is the topic, which is understood as a fragment of reality reflected in our minds and fixed with the help of language. Within the framework of the topic, certain lexical and grammatical material should be presented in all types of speech activity, which ensures better assimilation of linguistic material through the activation of auditory, visual and motor analyzers. The formation of communicatively significant skills and abilities is carried out with the help of a series of specially designed exercises, which present the studied lexical and grammatical material on a particular topic.

Practical classes contain a variety of exercises for practicing and consolidating language skills. Imitative, substitution, transformational, reproductive and speech tasks are aimed at the formation of the student's language, speech and communicative competencies in their professional field.

The traditional method of teaching the Russian language in schools and universities paid great attention to literate writing. However, this violated one of the basic laws of psycholinguistics, which is that all types of speech activity in the learning process should be formed in unity and in interconnection. In the 21st century, the anthropocentric orientation of linguistics made it possible to turn to the immediate goal of teaching the language as a means of communication.

The term "listening" is opposed to the term "listening". "Listening" - acoustic perception of the scale. The concept of listening, in turn, includes the perception and understanding of sounding speech. Listening is a complex aspect of speech activity. Many modern ypoel graduates practically do not possess this skill. Mastering listening makes it possible to realize educational, educational and developmental goals. Through listening, we nurture a culture of communication. In addition, human auditory memory develops.

Listening is a powerful tool for teaching a language, which makes it possible to master the sound side of the language being studied, its phonemic composition and intonation: rhythm, stress, melody. Listening as an action that is part of oral communicative activity is actively used in any oral communication subject to production, social or personal needs. Listening, as feedback from each speaker during speaking, allows you to exercise self-control over speech and know how correctly speech intentions are realized in sound form.

I. A. Zimnyaya identifies the following characteristics of listening as a type of speech activity: listening implements oral and direct communication; it is a reactive and receptive type of speech activity in the process of communication; the main form of the flow of listening is internal, uneven. Listening is the basis of communication, mastering oral communication begins with it. It consists of the ability to differentiate perceived sounds,

integrate them into semantic complexes, keep them in memory while listening, perform probabilistic forecasting and, based on the communication situation, understand the perceived sound chain. At the same time, the process of perception takes place at a certain normal pace, characteristic of a given language, from various sources, with natural interference of speech and non-speech nature .

The term listening was introduced into the literature by the American psychologist Brown, in Russia this term was introduced by Z.A. Kochkina in the article "What is listening?" in the 1960s.(before that, the term listening comprehension was used).Working with audio text consists of several stages: pre-text, text and post-text. Let's consider them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The pre-text stage includes work with the board, handouts and audio text fragments, as well as live educational communication. The main content of the stage: removing the language difficulties of the audio text (controlling the understanding of the most difficult sentences of the text, analyzing the meaning of individual words and phrases), training exercises based on the text, introducing and primary consolidation of new words, interpreting the use of lexical units and grammatical phenomena in the text, listening to individual fragments text. Pre-text orientation to the perception of speech by ear consists in setting pre-text questions, suggestions to title the text, tasks to confirm or refute the statements proposed by the teacher, choose correct, approximate and incorrect statements from a series of data, choose the correct answer to the question, reproduce contexts with keywords, etc. .

The text stage includes listening to the entire text and alternately separate paragraphs, semantic blocks. In the process of repeated listening to the text, students are offered the following types of work:

- 1.Selection of a paragraph heading.
- 2.Playing a keyword in context.
- 3.Paraphrasing.
- 4.Answers on questions.
- 5.Repeated listening to text or fragments.
- 6.Analysis of the use of language means.
- 7.Isolation of individual phrases on a certain basis.

The post-text stage includes question-answer work, word-by-word, concise, oriented retelling, expansion and continuation of the text by students, compiling a story by analogy, compiling a dialogue on the topic of the text, etc.

It is important to achieve the desire of students to learn to listen to speech and understand what is heard, to let them feel their capabilities, their progress. This increases their interest in learning a non-native language. In connection with listening, monologue speech develops, when students speak, after listening to the text, with independent communication and personal assessment, and the ability to speak in various situations within the framework of educational, labor, social and socio-cultural spheres of

communication is formed. With the help of active listening, a transition is made from speech at the sentence level to coherent monologue speech at the text level.

Listening is the basis of communication, mastering oral communication begins with it. Possession of listening allows a person to understand what is being told to him and adequately respond to what was said, helps to correctly state his answer to the opponent, which is the basis of oral speech.

When teaching Russian as a non-native language, information technologies are increasingly being used. Their use makes it possible to greatly increase the interest of students in the language, build the teacher's work in a new way, and implement the principle of interactivity. The audiovisual saturation of the educational material, accessibility, the ability to choose the material according to the degree of complexity contributes to the intensification of the process of its assimilation.

In modern life, the Internet has taken a dominant place among innovative technologies. There are many definitions of the Internet in the literature. The popular encyclopedia "Wikipedia" provides the following definition: "The Internet (eng. Internet) is a worldwide system of interconnected computer networks built on the basis of IP and IP packet routing. The Internet forms a global information space, serves as the physical basis for the World Wide Web (World Wide Web, WWW) and many other systems (protocols) for data transmission. Often referred to as the World Wide Web and the Global Network, as well as simply the Network. Currently, the word "Internet" most often refers to the World Wide Web and the information available on it, and not physical net.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The World Information Network gives a lot in the process of self-education, allows each user to choose their own path of learning. The use of electronic resources gives a new status to the independent work of students, in which learning becomes individual and independent in form, but in fact controlled and managed. Only a computer is able to carry out such a diverse form and content of communication with the student (informative, reference, consulting, productive, verbal, non-verbal - graphics, color, sound signaling).

The following forms of using information technology in language classes are possible:

- 1) creation of computer presentations by a teacher and a student;
- 2) work with sites focused on teaching the Russian language;
- 3) use of electronic dictionaries and encyclopedias;
- 4) performance by students of tasks with audio-video materials from the Internet;
- 5) distance language learning;
- 6) contact with the websites of educational institutions teaching the Russian language;
- 7) communication with native speakers in virtual communities, social networks.

Each form of information technology use has its own characteristics. According to E.A. Chertkova, "one of the techniques currently widely used for oral presentations are computer presentations that allow you to focus the attention of the audience on significant points of the information presented and create visual spectacular images in the form of

diagrams, diagrams, graphic compositions, etc. Considering the issue of using new technologies in teaching a foreign language at the initial stage, V.P. Kasyanova rightly noted that "independent creative work of students in creating computer presentations allows expanding the stock of active vocabulary, increasing interest in learning a foreign language and culture".

In the list of innovative tools, the use of an interactive whiteboard in the educational process should be highlighted. Promethean Planet (prometheanplanet.ru) is a specialized site that teaches how to work with an interactive whiteboard, allows you to exchange experience on its use, view online interactive classes, and take training. The teacher only needs to master the ActivStudio, ActivInspire software and interactive whiteboard, Activ Board, and he will be able to create bright, information-rich flipcharts. The site of the creative workshop of the Polytechnic College of Astana is one of the first Kazakhstani sites that started working in this direction. It contains tips and tricks for designing presentations, master classes, video courses on creating flipcharts, links to useful Internet resources. When teaching Russian as a non-native language, it is very important to present the material visually, and interactive whiteboards provide undoubted assistance in this. Students and teacher can jointly create a flipchart on the topic of the lesson. This develops not only the creative skills of students, but also the ability to work with computer technology.

Currently, the number of sites that professionally teach the Russian language is growing. These are Gra-mota.ru (gramota.ru), Culture of written speech (gramma.ru), Portal on the use of the Russian language and education in Russian in the CIS and Baltic states (russianforall.ru), Russian language and culture of speech (shpora07.narod.ru), the author's site of Oleg Efimovich Olshansky, professor of the Slavic State Pedagogical University, author of articles on the history of words and expressions in Russian (slovo.dn.ua), the Land of Words website, where the language is taught in a virtual school in a playroom form (wordsland.ru), Bukvoed blog containing facts from the history of the emergence of words and expressions, rules, interpretation of words (bukvoed.blogspot.com), etc. For a Russian language teacher in the 21st century, it is desirable to be able to actively use e-mail; create flipcharts, slide presentations; participate in virtual communities, popular network services; create your own microblogs and participate in others'; use electronic dictionaries, encyclopedias, participate in their creation; post materials of various forms on the network: audio, photo and video files; participate online in video conferences, Skype; organize independent work of students on the basis of digital technologies.

Of course, there are teachers who successfully integrate information and communication technologies into the practice of teaching a language. Our practice of working with ICT has shown that the best option is to integrate their ever-expanding capabilities into the framework of the traditional educational process, in which, nevertheless, ICT will not dominate, but will maximize the potential of integrative learning in the real educational process.

CONCLUSION

The worldwide information network makes it possible to make the learning process more efficient by involving most of the student's sensory components in the process of perception. With the aim of developing the communicative competence of students, the teacher must be able to organize work with Internet resources, master new methodological approaches to teaching. The interaction between the teacher and the student is carried out in the interactive mode. This facilitates the process of information exchange and increases the cognitive interest of students.

Thus, we see that the use of information technology is one of the necessary components of the educational process, including for the successful organization of independent work in teaching the Russian language to students with the state language of instruction. Informatization of education is an inevitable process, and a teacher of the humanities must be able to use the linguodidactic potential of Internet resources. In a technical university, the possession of innovative information technologies becomes especially important.

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